

The validation of the Vietnamese comprehensive score for financial toxicity (COST) in people with chronic disease

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Abstract

Objectives: This study aimed to explore the psychometric properties of the Vietnamese comprehensive score for financial toxicity (COST) among people with chronic disease.

Methods: We conducted a cross-sectional study involving 1,022 people with chronic disease in Can Tho City. Exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses were performed to assess construct validity, while Cronbach's alpha was used to evaluate the scale's reliability.

Results: Our EFA identified two factors explaining 55.0% of the cumulative variance. CFA indicated that the adjusted two-factor model demonstrated a good fit, with a comparative fit index of 0.96, a Tucker-Lewis index of 0.94, and an RMSEA of 0.062. COST scores were significantly correlated with monthly income ($p < 0.001$). The COST measure demonstrated good internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.82.

Conclusions: The COST is a valid and reliable measure for people with chronic disease in Vietnam. This scale can be applied in clinical practice to assess the impact of financial toxicity among people with chronic disease.

Keywords

chronic disease, financial toxicity, validation, Vietnam

Introduction

Chronic diseases, especially major non-communicable ones, which are caused by genetic, physiological, environmental, and behavioral factors, are the leading cause of death globally, accounting for about 41 million deaths annually (71% of all deaths) (World Health Organization 2024). Chronic diseases such as diabetes, heart disease,

stroke, and cancer have been, and continue to be, some of the major causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide (Hacker 2024). Vietnam has begun to face an aging population, which, together with other risk factors such as tobacco use, alcohol consumption, and a diet high in salt and fat, contributes to the increasing burden of chronic diseases (Ba et al. 2019; Hoy et al. 2013). Chronic conditions are the leading causes of death in the country (Ba et

al. 2019), with the leading causes per 100,000 population including stroke (167.6), ischemic heart disease (65.6), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (36), and diabetes mellitus (31.2) (World Health Organization 2021).

Chronic diseases impose a high and catastrophic cost burden on patients and their families (Okediji et al. 2017). The cost of chronic disease is estimated to reach USD 47 trillion worldwide by 2030 (Hacker 2024). Compared to high-income countries, the burden of such diseases is more severe in low- and middle-income countries, including Vietnam, due to multiple challenges in appropriate treatment, prevention, and early detection (Ito et al. 2022). Because chronic diseases require prolonged treatment, they impose a greater financial burden than acute diseases (Ito et al. 2022). This financial burden has been found to predict and impair quality of life and cost-related treatment nonadherence (Xu et al. 2024). In Vietnam, a report found that the presence of chronic conditions was associated with a 2.5-fold higher likelihood of cost-related medication nonadherence compared to those without chronic conditions (Tran et al. 2025). Therefore, screening and assessing the level of financial burden due to chronic diseases is necessary to understand the economic impact that patients are suffering and thereby suggest necessary intervention solutions. This financial burden raises ethical concerns about equity in access to care, as patients in lower socioeconomic groups are disproportionately affected (Ruger 2012), and highlights the responsibility of health systems to ensure financial risk protection and equitable access to essential services.

The term “financial toxicity” was first introduced in 2009 (Sideris et al. 2025) and is increasingly used to reflect the economic burden borne by individuals with chronic diseases (Tran et al. 2024a). Financial toxicity refers to the adverse effects experienced by patients as a result of the financial demands associated with cancer care. It encompasses both direct expenses paid out-of-pocket and indirect costs, along with shifts in a person’s or household’s financial stability caused by the process of diagnosis, treatment, survivorship, or palliative care. These financial pressures can lead to both physical and emotional distress and may influence health-related decisions, potentially resulting in poorer treatment outcomes (COSA 2022). To measure financial toxicity, the comprehensive score for financial toxicity (COST) scale was developed; however, its original version was constructed for the cancer population (de Souza et al. 2014). The COST scale is a unidimensional instrument consisting of 11 statements that assess patients’ perceived financial toxicity. Respondents rate each statement on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (“not at all”) to 4 (“very much”), with total scores ranging from 0 to 44; lower scores indicate greater financial toxicity. In recent years, this scale has also been applied to other chronic diseases such as diabetes (Patel et al. 2022) and chronic kidney disease (Silva et al. 2023), as well as disease groups related to cardiometabolism, pain management, pulmonary problems, immunology, and many other medical fields (Pavela et al. 2021). In Vietnam, the COST

scale has been localized and validated in cancer patients. However, its validity to assess financial stress in other chronic diseases in Vietnam has not been explored (Tran et al. 2024a). Given the growing burden of financial stress in chronic disease management and the demonstrated utility of the COST instrument in oncology, evaluating its application in broader chronic disease populations is both timely and necessary. Therefore, the aim of this study was to explore the psychometric properties of the Vietnamese COST among chronic patients.

Method

Study design and settings

A cross-sectional study was conducted among patients with chronic disease in Can Tho City. The area comprises nine administrative units, including five urban districts and four rural districts. For this study, one urban district and one rural district were randomly selected. From each selected administrative unit, six communes or wards were randomly chosen. In total, 12 sites (communes/wards) were included in the study. Based on the list of chronic patients managed at commune or ward health stations, each study site conveniently selected the first 100 patients appearing on the list. Eligible participants were adults (≥ 18 years) with chronic illnesses. Individuals who were unwilling to participate or unable to provide responses during the interview were excluded. This study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee in Biomedical Research of Nam Can Tho University (No. 31/YSH/PCT-HĐĐĐ). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection.

Data collection

Trained health science students conducted face-to-face interviews and completed printed questionnaires with chronically ill patients in their homes. Data were collected from April to May 2025.

Instruments

The Vietnamese version of the comprehensive score for financial toxicity (COST) instrument, previously validated in cancer patients, was used in this study to further validate it among individuals with various chronic diseases. A detailed description of the Vietnamese version of the COST can be found in a previous study (Tran et al. 2024a). The scale comprises 11 statements rated on a 5-point scale from 0 to 4. Several negatively worded questions were reverse-coded to ensure accurate scoring. The total score, ranging from 0 to 44, was calculated by summing all responses, with higher scores indicating greater financial well-being. The questionnaire was pilot-tested on 30 participants to ensure clarity and relevance prior to official implementation.

Socio-demographic characteristics were also collected, including gender; age (years); area of residence (urban, rural); marital status (married, single/widowed/divorced); education level (below lower secondary, lower secondary, upper secondary, or higher); occupation (stable income, unstable income, no income); monthly income (<8 million VND, ≥8 million VND); number of family members (<4, ≥4); and health insurance status (yes, no).

Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 22.0. Continuous variables were summarized as mean and standard deviation (SD), while categorical variables were described as frequency and percentage. T-tests and ANOVA were used to investigate the association between participant characteristics and COST scores. Ceiling and floor effects were assessed based on the distribution of COST scores. If more than 15% of individuals achieved either the highest or lowest possible total score, this was interpreted as evidence of a ceiling or floor effect (Terwee et al. 2007).

Construct validity was assessed using exploratory factor analysis (EFA), confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), and known-groups validity. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) index and Bartlett's test of sphericity, along with skewness and kurtosis, were used to assess the suitability of the data for factor analysis. Normality was defined as skewness between -2 and +2 and kurtosis between -7 and +7 (Hair et al. 2010). The structure of the COST scale was examined using EFA, applying the principal component method and Varimax rotation. Factors were retained if they had an eigenvalue greater than 1 and a factor loading of 0.50 or higher. CFA was performed using jamovi version 2.6.13 and AMOS version 20.0. Model fit was evaluated using multiple indices, including the comparative fit index (CFI) and Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), with values greater than 0.90 indicating acceptable fit (Tran et al. 2024a; Yu et al. 2021). The root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) was also examined, with values below 0.07 considered indicative of good fit (Tran et al. 2024a). All standardized factor loadings were required to be at least 0.5 (Cheung et al. 2024). Known-group validity was tested by comparing COST scores across monthly income groups.

Internal consistency reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. A Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.80 or higher was considered indicative of good reliability. Corrected item-total correlations were used to evaluate the contribution of each item to the overall scale, with correlations of 0.30 or greater regarded as satisfactory (Kim et al. 2025).

Results

Study participants

A total of 1,022 participants were included in the final analysis, yielding an 85.2% response rate (Table 1). In this study

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of participants (n = 1022).

Characteristics		Full sample (N = 1022), n (%)	COST score, Mean (SD)	P value [†]
Gender	Man	363 (35.5)	26.06 (7.35)	0.063
	Woman	659 (64.5)	25.15 (7.51)	
Age (year)	< 60	405 (39.6)	25.56 (7.23)	0.762
	≥ 60	617 (60.4)	25.41 (7.62)	
	Mean (SD)	61.81 (11.81)		
Residential area	Urban	185 (18.1)	24.87 (7.06)	0.227
	Rural	837 (81.9)	25.6 (7.55)	
Marital status	Married	844 (82.7)	25.84 (7.34)	<0.001
	Single/Widowed/ Divorced	178 (17.4)	23.74 (7.82)	
Education level	Below lower secondary	525 (51.4)	24.62 (7.62)	<0.001
	Lower secondary	344 (33.7)	25.89 (7.08)	
	Upper secondary or higher	153 (15)	27.44 (7.35)	
Occupation	Stable income jobs	48 (4.7)	28.25 (7.09)	0.008
	Unstable income jobs	464 (45.4)	25.74 (7.36)	
	No income	510 (49.9)	24.96 (7.54)	
Monthly income (million VND)	< 8	887 (86.8)	24.88 (7.42)	<0.001
	≥ 8	135 (13.2)	29.35 (6.55)	
Number of family members	< 4	367 (35.9)	25.18 (7.80)	0.356
	≥ 4	655 (64.1)	25.63 (7.27)	
	Mean (SD)	4.19 (1.88)		
Health insurance	Yes	969 (94.8)	25.51 (7.54)	0.378
	No	53 (5.2)	24.75 (5.94)	

†P value was calculated using T-test and ANOVA.

sample, participants were diagnosed with the following main groups of conditions: cardiometabolic diseases (n = 872); musculoskeletal and pain-related disorders (n = 356); pulmonary conditions (n = 43); gastrointestinal and hepatic diseases (n = 26); renal and neurological conditions (n = 18); and oncological diseases (n = 16). The total number of diagnoses exceeded the sample size of 1,022 because some participants had multiple chronic conditions. The mean age of participants was 61.8 years (standard deviation 11.8), with a range from 24 to 98 years. Approximately 82.7% of participants were married, only 4.7% had stable income jobs, and 86.8% reported a monthly family income of <8 million VND.

Distributional characteristics

Examination of floor and ceiling effects revealed that only 0.1% of participants achieved the minimum score (3.00) and 0.3% achieved the maximum score (44.00) on the COST scale. As both proportions were below the conventional threshold of 15%, no substantive floor or ceiling effects were detected.

Construct validity

The dataset was randomly divided into two parts: Part 1 (n = 482) was used for EFA, and Part 2 (n = 540) for CFA. The data were suitable for EFA, as indicated by Bartlett's

test of sphericity ($\chi^2 = 1859.757, p < 0.001$) and a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of 0.85. Furthermore, all variables had skewness values ranging from -0.85 to 0.20 and kurtosis values ranging from -1.07 to 1.67 (Table 2). These values fell within the acceptable limits (skewness ± 2 ; kurtosis ± 7), indicating that the data were normally distributed and thus suitable for EFA. Two factors were extracted, each having eigenvalues greater than 1 and together accounting for 55.0% of the cumulative variance. The first factor includes seven items with factor loadings ranging from 0.59 to 0.74 and was named the “negative psychosocial response”. The second factor includes four items with factor loadings ranging from 0.65 to 0.85 and was named the “positive wealth status”. The items and factor loadings of COST are presented in Table 2.

The CFA results showed that the adjusted two-fac-

Table 2. Distributional characteristics and factor loading of COST scale (n = 482).

Item	Skewness	Kurtosis	Factor 1	Factor 2
COST 3	0.20	-1.05	0.739	
COST 9	-0.38	-0.66	0.737	
COST 10	-0.55	-0.59	0.724	
COST 8	-0.85	1.67	0.675	
COST 4	-0.19	-0.95	0.652	
COST 5	-0.43	-0.75	0.618	
COST 2	0.08	-1.07	0.592	
COST 11	-0.35	-0.68		0.853
COST 7	-0.45	-0.76		0.839
COST 6	-0.31	-0.99		0.804
COST 1	-0.37	-0.74		0.647
Variance explained (%)			30.1	24.9

Extraction method: Principal component analysis; Rotation method: Varimax with Kaiser normalization.

tor model demonstrated a better fit than other models, with a CFI of 0.96, a TLI of 0.94, and an RMSEA of 0.062 (Table 3). The standardized factor loadings ranged from 0.56 to 0.78 (Fig. 1), which is within the appropriate range.

Regarding known-group validity, the COST was able to differentiate between groups with different monthly incomes. Specifically, groups with incomes lower than 8 million VND (mean = 24.88) had lower COST scores (corresponding to a greater financial impact) than groups with incomes higher than 8 million VND (mean = 29.35, $p < 0.001$), as shown in Table 1. In addition, marital status ($p < 0.001$), education level ($p < 0.001$), and occupation ($p = 0.008$) were also significantly associated with COST scores.

Table 3. Comparison of the factor structure of COST scale (11 items) using confirmatory factor analysis (n = 540).

Version	Chi-square/df	CFI	TLI	RMSEA
One-factor model	13.8	0.73	0.65	0.154
One-factor model (adjusted) [†]	7.10	0.88	0.83	0.106
Two-factor model	3.74	0.94	0.92	0.071
Two-factor model (adjusted) [‡]	3.10	0.96	0.94	0.062

[†]Allowing for correlations between error terms specified in modification indices (items 7 and 11; items 8 and 9). [‡]Allowing for correlations between error terms specified in modification indices (items 8 and 9).

Figure 1. Structure of items in the COST scale (n = 540).

Reliability

The Cronbach’s alpha coefficient for the COST measure was 0.82, indicating good internal consistency. The corrected item-total correlations for COST ranged from 0.39 to 0.61, demonstrating satisfactory correlations with the total score and thus confirming high internal consistency reliability. Items 3 (0.61) and 8 (0.61) had the highest corrected correlations with the total COST score, suggesting that they significantly contributed to the measurement of financial impact.

Table 4. Scores and reliability of the COST scale (n = 1022).

Item code	Mean (SD)	Corrected item-total correlation	Cronbach’s alpha if item deleted	Cronbach’s alpha
COST 1	2.23 (1.13)	0.387	0.817	
COST 2	2.14 (1.15)	0.388	0.817	
COST 3	2.03 (1.23)	0.610	0.795	
COST 4	2.32 (1.1)	0.487	0.808	
COST 5	2.43 (1.17)	0.428	0.813	
COST 6	2.14 (1.15)	0.514	0.805	
COST 7	2.23 (1.15)	0.433	0.813	
COST 8	2.56 (1.09)	0.609	0.797	
COST 9	2.51 (1.07)	0.592	0.798	
COST 10	2.67 (1.09)	0.497	0.807	
COST 11	2.21 (1.12)	0.449	0.811	
Overall scale	25.47 (7.46)			0.822

Discussion

This study is the first, to our knowledge, to provide evidence of the reliability and validity of a financial stress measurement instrument related to the management of various chronic diseases in Vietnam.

EFA revealed a two-factor structure of the COST scale in this study, including “negative psychosocial response” (comprising seven items: COST 2, 3, 4, 5, 8, 9, and 10) and “positive wealth status” (comprising four items: COST 1, 6, 7, and 11). The grouping of items into each factor, as well as the naming of the two identified factors, is similar to results reported in previous studies (Tran et al. 2024a; Yu et al. 2021).

The CFA results also support the two-factor structure, as demonstrated by satisfactory fit indices for CFI, TLI, and RMSEA. In the initial development of the scale, the structure was reported as unidimensional (de Souza et al. 2014). Therefore, we also tested the fit of the one-factor model, and the results showed that its fit indices were inferior to those of the two-factor model. In addition, the one-factor model explained only 37.8% of the variance, whereas the two-factor model explained 55%. This level of variance explained by the two-factor model is consistent with the acceptable threshold of at least 50% of total variance explained by the retained factors (Streiner 1994). Therefore, the Vietnamese version of COST with two factors was considered appropriate, consistent with findings from other studies (Patel et al. 2022; Tran et al. 2024a).

COST also differentiated between patients in the low- and high-income groups, consistent with the study hypothesis and previous findings (Kim et al. 2025). Income is a factor affecting financial toxicity, as individuals with limited financial resources are more vulnerable to the burden of medical costs (Tran et al. 2024b). These results further support the known-groups validity of the COST-PROM tool in assessing financial toxicity specifically and reliably among patient groups with varying economic backgrounds.

The internal consistency of the COST was comparable to both the initial validation of the instrument (de Souza et al. 2014, 2017) and studies that validated the instrument in other languages (Fradelos et al. 2023; Yu et al. 2021), including Vietnamese (Tran et al. 2024a). The adjusted item-total correlations, which were within acceptable limits, indicated that all 13 items of the COST contributed to the measurement of financial impact.

In this study, the average COST score was 25.47, which exceeded values reported in earlier research (Patel et al. 2025; Silva et al. 2023). This result may indicate that participants experienced lower financial distress, potentially influenced by factors such as comprehensive health insurance coverage or reduced treatment costs. By 2024, more than 94.2% of the Vietnamese population had participated in health insurance, moving closer to the goal of universal health coverage (Viet Nam Social Security 2025). These findings underscore the importance of calibrating the COST scale according to population characteristics to ensure adequate sensitivity in assessing financial toxicity.

The validated Vietnamese version of the COST tool in this study may be useful in both clinical and public health settings. For example, it can serve as a screening instrument to identify chronic patients experiencing financial difficulties. Early detection is important for guiding interventions by clinicians and policymakers, including financial counseling and referral to social support services. This approach can help promote more comprehensive and patient-centered care by addressing the financial burden of treatment.

This study achieved a high response rate (85.2%), which enhances the reliability of the results and reduces the risk of non-response bias. With a sample size of 1,022 individuals representing diverse chronic illnesses, the study offers insights that may be applicable to a wide range of patients living with long-term conditions.

Several limitations should be noted. First, due to its cross-sectional nature, the study cannot capture changes in financial toxicity over the course of treatment. Second, although the initial selection of study sites was conducted randomly to enhance representativeness, the use of convenience sampling to recruit patients at each site may introduce selection bias. Our sample consisted primarily of patients with chronic conditions, with small sample sizes for some specific conditions. This limits the ability to generalize our findings to specific chronic conditions. Third, the study did not assess convergent validity, as it did not compare COST with related measures such as life treatment burden, psychological distress, or quality of life. This represents a significant limitation, as convergent validity is critical for confirming the conceptual relevance of patient-reported outcome measures. Future studies should examine the relationship between COST and these related measures to support its validity in different clinical and cultural contexts.

Conclusion

The study confirms the validity and reliability of the Vietnamese version of the COST instrument in a chronic patient population. This is the first validation study of COST in relation to multiple chronic conditions in Vietnam. The scale can be used in diverse healthcare settings—such as outpatient clinics, community health programs, and health insurance eligibility screening—to measure the impact of financial toxicity in chronic patients, thereby providing a basis for interventions addressing financial toxicity in chronic diseases. Future studies may apply this validated tool for longitudinal tracking of financial toxicity, exploring differences across specific disease types and between rural and urban populations, or integrating it with electronic health records.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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